

Osmium (VIII) Catalysed Oxidation of Dioxane with Alkaline Potassium Ferricyanide

U.S. Mehrotra and S. P. Mushran

The oxidation of dioxane with alkaline potassium ferricyanide using osmium (VIII) as catalyst has been studied and it has been found that the rate of reaction is independent of the concentration of the oxidant and is proportional to the alkali concentration. The reaction is found to be of first order with respect to the substrate and half order with respect to the catalyst concentration. Formaldehyde has been detected as the oxidation product. The values of energy of activation and the entropy of activation are found to be 11.84 K.cal. mole⁻¹ and -39.36 e.u. respectively. The following rate law has been found to govern the reaction

$$-\frac{d(\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-})}{dt} = k' [\text{Dioxane}] [\text{OH}^-] [\text{Os}(\text{VIII})]^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

EXPERIMENTAL AND RESULTS

All the reagents used were of AnalaR (BDH) quality and the solutions were prepared in conductivity water.

The requisite amounts of dioxane, sodium hydroxide, and the catalyst (osmium tetroxide in sodium hydroxide solution) solutions of desired concentration were taken in a reaction bottle. The mixture and alkaline potassium ferricyanide solutions of desired concentration were separately kept in a thermostat maintained at a constant temperature. The reaction was started by adding requisite volume of alkaline potassium ferricyanide solution. 5 ml of aliquots were withdrawn at fixed intervals of time and were poured into a conical flask containing 10 mls of 2 N hydrochloric acid to quench the reaction. The ferrocyanide formed during the reaction was estimated by titrating it against a standard ceric sulphate solution using N-phenyl anthranilic acid as an indicator. In order to maintain a constant pH during the course of the reaction, borate buffer, has been used.

The rate of osmium (VIII) catalysed oxidation of dioxane with alkaline potassium ferricyanide has been found to be independent of the oxidant concentration as seen from the kinetic data presented in Table I where zero order rate constants remain fairly constant.

Effect of varying the concentration of Oxidant: The reaction has been studied at four concentrations of the oxidant and it has been found that the zero order constants are fairly good which confirms that the rate of the reaction is independent of the concentration of the oxidant. Table 2 shows the zero order constants at different concentrations of the oxidant.

TABLE I

Showing the values of the zero order constants with respect to the oxidant

Dioxane = 2.5%, $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{--}$ = 0.003 M, OH^- = 0.005 M,
 Os(VIII) = 1.57×10^{-5} M. Temp. 35°

Time in mts.	Vol. of 0.002 M $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ in ml.	Zero order constants $x/t \times 10^2$
0	0.24	—
10	0.66	4.2
20	1.08	4.2
30	1.52	4.4
40	1.94	4.2
50	2.40	4.6
60	2.82	4.2
70	3.20	3.8
80	3.60	4.0
90	3.96	3.6

Average $x/t = 4.15 \times 10^{-2}$

TABLE 2

Zero order constants at different concentrations of the oxidant

Dioxane = 2.5%, OH^- = 0.005M, Os(VIII) = 1.57×10^{-5} M, Temp. 35°

Concentration of $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ M	Zero order constants $\times 10^5$ (mole/min)
0.001	8.60
0.002	8.40
0.003	8.30
0.004	8.20

Effect of varying the concentration of Dioxane: The reaction has been studied at four different concentrations of dioxane. Table 3 shows that the zero order constants are proportional to the concentration of the substrate. The reaction is therefore of first order with respect to dioxane.

TABLE 3

Variation of rate constants with varying dioxane concentration

$\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{--}$ = 0.003M, OH^- = 0.005M, Os(VIII) = 1.57×10^{-5} M, Temp. 35°

Concentration of Dioxane %	Zero order constants $\times 10^5$ (mole/min)
0.625	2.20
1.250	4.40
2.500	8.30
5.000	16.00

Effect of varying the Alkali concentration: The reaction has been studied at four different concentrations of alkali. It has been observed that zero order rate constants change directly as the alkali concentration. Table 4 shows the effect of varying the hydroxyl ion concentration on the zero order constants.

TABLE 4

Variation of rate constants with varying hydroxyl ion concentration

Dioxane = 2.5%, $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-} = 0.003\text{M}$, $\text{Os}(\text{VIII}) = 1.57 \times 10^{-5}\text{M}$, Temp. 35° .

Concentration of hydroxyl ion M	Zero order constants $\times 10^5$ (mole/min)
0.00125	2.12
0.00250	4.08
0.00500	8.20
0.01000	15.90

It is evident from the above table that an increase in pH results in an increase in the rate constants.

Effect of varying the catalyst concentration: The reaction has also been studied at four concentrations of catalyst, osmium (VIII). Table 5 gives the values of zero order rate constants at different concentrations of the catalyst at 35° .

TABLE 5

Variation of rate constants with varying catalyst concentration

Dioxane = 2.5%, $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-} = 0.003\text{M}$, $\text{OH}^- = 0.005\text{M}$

Concentration of catalyst $\times 10^5\text{M}$	Zero order constants $\times 10^5$ (mole/min)		
	30°	35°	40°
0.3925	3.2	4.3	5.8
0.7850	4.4	6.1	8.2
1.5700	6.0	8.3	11.2
3.1400	8.9	12.2	16.0

It has been found that the plot of the square root of the concentration of the catalyst versus zero order constants gives a straight line and hence the reaction is of half order with respect to the catalyst. (Fig. 1)

Fig. 1

Effect of Temperature: Table 6 shows the effect of temperature on the reaction rate at a constant concentration of the reactants.

TABLE 6

Variation of rate constants with temperature

Dioxane=2.5%, $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{--} = 0.003 \text{ M}$, $\text{OH}^- = 0.005 \text{ M}$, $\text{Os}(\text{VIII}) = 1.57 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$

Temperature in °C	30	35	40
Zero order constants $\times 10^5$ (mole/min)	6.00	8.30	11.20

The value of temperature coefficient of the reaction is found to be 1.86 and the energy of activation and the entropy of activation for the reaction came out to be 11.84 K.cal mole⁻¹ and -39.36 e.u. respectively. The value of frequency factor has been calculated out to be 18.37×10^3 mole/min. Formaldehyde is the oxidation product which has been detected with chromotropic acid which develops a violet colour in sulphuric acid media. The stoichiometry of the reaction is therefore represented as follows:

DISCUSSION

Pode and Waters¹ have reported that dioxane having a ring structure is a stable compound and is not oxidised by weak oxidants. According to them hexavalent manganese fails to oxidise dioxane. Ghosh and Misra² have reported the oxidation of dioxane by potassium peroxydisulphate in presence of silver(I) as catalyst. Alkaline potassium ferricyanide is a strong oxidising agent and has extensively been used to oxidise many organic compounds³. At low concentrations of alkali it has been found that potassium ferricyanide is ineffective in oxidising dioxane. Osmium (VIII), which has been reported as a general catalyst for the oxidation in alkaline media by Solymosi^{4,5} has therefore been employed and it has been seen that it catalyses the reaction satisfactorily.

The experimental data obtained for the osmium-(VIII) catalysed oxidation of dioxane by potassium ferricyanide shows that the rate of the reaction is independent of the concentration of the oxidant. The reaction shows first order dependence with respect to the substrate and alkali concentration which is in accordance with the results obtained by Speakman and Waters⁶ during the oxidation of some organic compounds by alkaline potassium ferricyanide. They have shown that in the oxidations with alkaline ferricyanide, the rate of the oxidation is proportional to the alkali concentration.

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It has been noted that the *pH* of the reaction mixture falls during the course of the reaction. The *pH* was maintained at a constant level by making use of borate buffer. Kolthoff and coworkers⁷ have also employed buffers during their studies of the oxidation of some organic compounds by the same oxidants.

We suggest that the reaction occurs in three steps. The first step involves a reversible equilibria between the substrate and the hydroxyl ion which forms an intermediate anion as follows.—

This intermediate anion is subsequently oxidised by osmium (VIII) and gives the product, osmium(VIII) being reduced to osmium(VI) according to step (2) as below:

The osmium (VI) so formed is immediately oxidized to osmium (VIII) by alkaline potassium ferricyanide according to the step (3) as follows:

Since the reaction is independent of the oxidant concentration, it is evident that the step (3) is fast. Step (1) shows that the oxidation is proportional to the hydroxyl ion whilst step (2) is slow and rate controlling and explains the results of our investigations. The formation of Os(VI) intermediate is in accordance with the work of Criegae⁸ on the oxidation of alkenes.

Applying the steady state treatment and taking into account the above steps it can easily be shown that the rate law equation is as follows:

$$-\frac{d(\text{Fe(CN)}_6^{3-})}{dt} = k k_3 [\text{Dioxane}] [\text{OH}^-] [\text{Os(VIII)}]^{1/2}$$

This rate law equation for the alkaline potassium ferricyanide oxidation of dioxane catalysed by osmium (VIII) is amply supported by the experimental results.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
ALLAHABAD UNIVERSITY,
ALLAHABAD, INDIA.

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